

Studies in Thiadiazoles: Part VI. Synthesis of some 2-Substituted-5-Mercapto-1,3,4-Thiadiazoles and Related Compounds

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Several 2-substituted-5-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles have been synthesised. Their sodium salts have been condensed with appropriate alkyl and aralkyl halides and the resultant sulphides oxidised to corresponding sulphones. These compounds are expected to display pesticidal activity.

SH-group is just as important a toxophore as -OH, especially to fungi¹ and when a heterocyclic compound contains an -SH group adjacent to a nitrogen atom, useful fungitoxic compounds are often obtained because of the possibility of chelation^{2,3}. The 2-mercapto thiadiazoles fulfill these requirements and therefore it appeared worthwhile to synthesise these compounds with a view to studying their fungicidal activity.

A large number of benzylphenyl sulphides have been patented as acaricides⁴ and a variety of sulphones are active against mites^{4,5,6}. Heterocyclic sulphides and sulphones seem to have been little studied; therefore evaluation of the pesticidal activity of thiadiazolyl sulphides and sulphones also appeared desirable.

Seven 2-substituted-5-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles were prepared by the reaction of 4-aryltiosemicarbazides with carbon disulphide in dimethylformamide⁷. These were condensed with appropriate alkyl and aralkylhalides in alkaline medium⁸ and the resulting sulphides were oxidised with 30% H₂O₂ in glacial acetic acid following the method of Bambar⁹ to yield the required sulphones.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Aryltiosemicarbazides were prepared according to the method of Kazakov *et al*¹⁰

2-Arylamino-5-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles. — A mixture of appropriate 4-aryltiosemicarbazide (0.1M), carbon disulphide (0.1M) and dimethylformamide (30 ml) was

1. Horsfall and Rich, "*Contribs. Boyes Thompson Inst.*", 1951, 16, 313.
2. Albert *et al*, *Brit. Jour. Expt. Path.*, 1947, 28, 69.
3. B. P. 790, 197/1958; *Chem. Abst.*, 1958, 52, 15581.
4. Metcalf, "*Organic Insecticides*", p. 198.
5. Dutch, 81359/1956.
6. B. P., 792, 045/1958.
7. *Chem. Abst.*, 1964, 58, 2951.
8. Stevenson *et al*, *Chem. Abst.*, 1958, 52, 15581.
9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 668.
10. *Chem. Abst.*, 1961., 55, 23415.

refluxed on water bath for 1 to 1½ hr. at 70-80°. The product on cooling separated as a crystalline solid which was purified as usual. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in table I.

TABLE I

Serial No. Ar.	M.P.°C.	%yield	Formula	% Sulphur	
				Found	Reqd.
1. Phenyl	204	80	---	---	---
2. 4-Fluorophenyl	114	82	C ₈ H ₆ N ₃ S ₂ F	28.32	28.19
3. 4-Methylphenyl	215	81	---	---	---
4. 2-Methylphenyl	196	74	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	28.24	28.69
5. Benzyl	136	65	---	---	---
6. 4-Bromophenyl	178-79	68	C ₈ H ₆ N ₃ S ₂ Br	22.16	22.22
7. 4-Chlorophenyl	192	69	C ₈ H ₆ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	26.80	26.28

Alkyl(aralkyl)-(5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) Sulphides.—To a mixture of 2-arylamino-5-mercapto-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole (0.1M) and alkyl or aralkylhalide (0.1M) in ethanol (50 ml) was gradually added a solution of sodium hydroxide (0.1M). The solution was refluxed for 1 to 1½ hr. Upon cooling and pouring into water, a precipitate was obtained. This was filtered, washed well with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

These compounds are recorded in table II.

TABLE II

Serial No. Ar.	M.P.°C.	Yield	Formula	% Sulphur	
				Found	Reqd.
R = Methyl					
1. Phenyl	118-20	62	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	28.64	28.78
2. <i>p</i> -Tolyl	175-77	94	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	26.78	27.00
3. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	290	47	C ₉ H ₈ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	24.44	24.9
4. Benzyl	110-11	54	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	27.25	27.00
5. <i>m</i> -Fluorophenyl	145	83	C ₉ H ₈ N ₃ S ₂ F	26.33	26.55
R = Benzyl					
6. Phenyl	145	56	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	21.14	21.40
7. <i>p</i> -Tolyl	140-42	52	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	20.36	20.40
8. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	282-83	33	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	18.94	19.19
9. Benzyl	98-100	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	20.11	20.44
10. <i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	158	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ S ₂ F	20.40	20.18

Alkyl/aralkyl-(5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) Sulphones.—To an appropriate thiazolylsulphide (0.01M) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml.) was added H_2O_2 (10.5 ml, 30%) and the mixture heated gently for 30-45 min. under reflux. Upon cooling and pouring into cold water, the required sulphone was precipitated. This was purified in the usual way.

The sulphone thus obtained are listed below in table III.

TABLE III

Serial No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Yield	Formula	%Nitrogen		%Sulphur	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
R = Methyl								
1.	Phenyl	125	88	$C_9H_9N_3O_2S_2$	16.13	16.47	24.92	25.05
2.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	230-32	58	$C_{10}H_{11}N_3O_2S_2$	15.37	15.61	23.17	23.79
3.	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	295	78	$C_9H_8N_3O_2S_2Cl$	14.67	14.54	21.85	22.10
4.	R = Benzyl							
4.	Phenyl	145	91	$C_{13}H_{13}N_3O_2S_2$	12.51	12.68	19.26	19.33
5.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	130-32	68	$C_{16}H_{17}N_3O_2S_2$	12.32	12.17	16.39	18.55
6.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	304-5	62	$C_{13}H_{11}N_3O_2S_2Cl$	11.21	11.49	17.41	17.53
7.	Benzyl	100-01	76	$C_{16}H_{17}N_3O_2S_2$	11.98	12.17	18.67	18.55
8.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	165-66	55	$C_{13}H_{11}N_3O_2S_2F$	11.78	12.03	18.46	18.43

The pesticidal activity of some of these compounds has been evaluated and some work is still under investigation. This will be published in due course.

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